

Co-funded by the European Union

DEN-CUPID

Digital Educational Network For Cultural
Projects Implementation And Direction

2nd Newsletter

Dissemination Activities

Following the project's Kick off Meeting that took place in Trikala (November 2016) all the partners focused on disseminating the project even further via posters, leaflets and the project's official site <http://den-cupid.eu/> connected to social media, particularly to facebook

E-trikala S.A participated with a stand at the **Major Cities Of Europe Conference in Zagreb** during 12-14 June 2017, where DEN-CuPID was promoted via poster, leaflets and a presentation. What is more, a small description of the project was distributed with the conference newsletter. The Project was disseminated even further via press releases both in English and Greek.

*Major Cities Of Europe Conference
in Zagreb, June 2014*

Time Heritage had an **One-day conference of the Regional Association of Municipalities of Thessaly on Thermal Tourism and Local Administration** on the 27th of May 2017 where DEN-CuPID was briefly presented during the conference, particularly in relation to the forthcoming training events,

<http://www.pedthessalias.gr/2012-01-12-13-14-02/nea-anakoinoseis-deltia-tupou/item/395-hmerida-ths-ped-iamatikos-tourismos.html>

What is more and in collaboration with University of Patras they presented DEN-CuPID via poster and leaflets at the **3rd Conference of ΕΣΔΙΑΠΟΚ (Cultural Heritage Management Consultants' Society): "Cultural Heritage and Universal Challenges (31/3-1/4/2017)** and initiated the facebook page of DEN-CuPID

<https://www.facebook.com/dencupid.eu/>.

3rd Conference of ΕΣΔΙΑΠΟΚ, April, 2017

The Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies (University of Patras) of Patras also disseminated Den-CuPID project to the students and other interested parties in the context of the **Parrhasian Heritage Park Field School (8/8/2017)**, whereas Amphictyony presented the project via an oral presentation in the course of the **Annual General Convention of E.G.T.C. Amphictyony (17/3/2017)**.

UNESCO Hellas promoted the project at the **Meeting of Coordinators/Teachers of UNESCO's Associated School Project Network (ASPnet)** that took place at the Greek Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs, (8/5/2017).

Title: Meeting of Coordinators/teachers of Unesco Associated School Project Network, May 2017

Futuro Digitale presented Den-Cupid project via an oral presentation in front of 150 high school students in the context of open-data applied on culture & mobility programmes(20/4/2017)

<http://www.futurodigitale.org/it/iniziativa-open-culture/>

Furthermore, Futuro Digitale organized four “Open Culture” events at the **Public Library Cori (near Rome)**, (9 and 23 March, 13 and 27 April 2017) on the usage of open data applied to culture, cultural enterprises and Den-Cupid project.

March- April 2017, open-data collecting walks

After the theoretical preparation of participants, different open-data collecting walks were held, inviting new people and disseminating the project. Finally, UBBSLA presented the project during the local info day for energy efficiency and resilient cities on 22nd of June and in the local info day on culture heritage on the 14th of August in Varna.

Info days in Varna, June and August 2017

Platform

One of the project's intellectual outputs is the creation of an Educational platform, that will allow all stakeholders, trainees and people who are interested in learning about cultural management to study on line the educational material prepared by the project's partners and follow tests that will evaluate their level of understanding. Furthermore, the platform will serve as well as a networking space, where participants can communicate and share ideas among themselves or with experts and even attend via live streaming any future workshops. In the following period a small testing phase will take place, to test the educational platform on a limited number of participants that will give a valuable feedback before the platform is officially presented to the public

Survey (Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies - University of Patras)

An online survey has been designed and carried out with the aim to assess the situation regarding local cultural assets and practices, and record the needs and attitudes of those involved in cultural/heritage projects, such as local authorities, NGOs, cultural societies, private institutions and local businesses. Focus was mainly centered on the programme's participating partner countries: Bulgaria, Greece, Italy, Spain. The intention is to use the results so as to design and develop high quality and innovative tools and training courses for training and coaching municipalities' employees and local actors involved or interested in cultural management projects and ventures.

The initial questionnaire was drafted in English. Greek, Bulgarian, Spanish and Italian versions of the questionnaire were produced with the help of the partners. The partners have also helped to evaluate the content of the questionnaire and distribute the survey. VEA distributed the questionnaire to 168 public and private organizations. UBBSLA invited to participate in the survey 55 organizations whose insights were considered valuable for the survey. Futuro Digitale sent the questionnaire to all their contacts. Their contact group includes 22.000 recipients. Greek partners such as Amphictyony, E-Trikala, Time Heritage and University of Patras distributed the questionnaire to local municipalities and private organizations engaged in cultural heritage projects. The survey was set up with survey monkey and had been open for a period of five months (March to July). The survey comprised of 29 questions and was organized in five sections. The filled in questionnaires reached the number 195.

First Workshop (Vea Global)

The first workshop within the project took place in Zaragoza, Spain, from September 18th to 21st. Trainees from the countries that partners are from attended to the four days meeting: four from Italy, four from Bulgaria, eight from Greece and three from Spain.

First and second day presentations were focussed on Mujedar Art, Aljaferia Palace and the Managing Process of some public institutions like Unesco, Aragon Government and the Managing Service of Aljaferia Palace.

Third day presentations were focused on the experience of several institutions and private business who talked about their experience and work around the Cultural Heritage. Partners Time Heritage and University of Patras discussed about sustainability of Cultural Heritage, emphasizing the importance of raising public awareness and promoting sustainable tourism. Last day trainees learned some basic lessons about how to make a business plan. After that they worked in teams applying what they learned on a real example Veruela Monastery, located close to Zaragoza. During the workshop, trainees also had the opportunity to visit the most emblematic places of Zaragoza: Aljaferia Palace, the historic center of Zaragoza and Zaragoza Museum.

First Workshop in Zaragoza, September 2017

Partners Meeting and Next Workshop

Following the workshop, from 21 to 22 of September 2017, the second scheduled project meeting took place, where representatives from all partners participated, mostly to discuss about the results of the first workshop and organize the following workshop that will take place in Greece.

Partner's meeting in Veia Global headquarters, Zaragoza, September 2017

The next workshop will take place between 4-7 December 2017 in Trikala Greece, where trainees from 4 different countries will participate (Greece, Spain, Italy and Bulgaria). The main theme of the second workshop will be the development of a Theme Park and best practices on touristic development of the area.

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